

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1840	Titu Maiorescu	1857	1860	1914		Romanian literary critic and politician, founder of the Junimea Society	1840-1917
1840	Paul Meyer	1861		1917		French philologist	1840-1917
1840	August Leskien	1864	1864	1915		German linguist	1840-1916
1840	Alexander Riese	1864	1864	1914		German classical scholar	1840-1924
1840	Arthur Ludwich	1866	1866	1912		German classical philologist who specialized in Homeric studies	1840-1920
1840	Arthur Coke Burnell	1868		1882		British English civil servant who served in the Madras Presidency who was also a scholar in Sanskrit and Dravidian languages	1840-1882
1840	Adolph Francis Alphonse Bandelier	1879		1914		Swiss-American archaeologist who particularly explored the indigenous cultures of the American Southwest, Mexico, and South America	1840-1914
1840	Charles George Herbermann	1880		1914		German-American professor of Latin language and Literature and historian	1840-1916
1842	Berthold Delbrück	1863	1863	1912		German linguist	1842-1922
1841	Wilhelm Scherer	1864		1886		German philologist and historian of literature	1841-1886
1842	Eugen Bormann	1865	1865	1914		German-Austrian historian, known for his work in the field of Latin epigraphy	1842-1917
1841	Bernhard Egidius Konrad ten Brink	1865		1892		German philologist	1841-1892
1841	Gustave Le Bon	1866	1866	1920		French polymath whose areas of interest included anthropology, psychology, sociology, medicine, invention, and physics	1841-1931
1841	Francis Brinkley	1885		1912		British Irish newspaper owner, editor and scholar who resided in Meiji period Japan for over 40 years, where he was the author of numerous books on Japanese culture, art and architecture and an English-Japanese Dictionary	1841-1912
1842	Hermann Breymann	1868	1868	1910		German philologist and pedagogue	1842-1910
1842	Vilhelm Thomsen	1869	1869	1927		Danish linguist and Turkologist	1842-1927
1842	Moritz Trautmann	1871	1871	1920		German Anglist	1842-1920
1842	Giuseppe Sergi	1874		1916		Italian anthropologist of the early twentieth century	1841-1936

1842	Ella Sophia Armitage	1877		1919 w	British English historian and archaeologist.	1841-1931
1842	Sylvester Primer	1880	1880	1912	American linguist and philologist	1842-1912
1842	Otto Ammon	1883	No	1916	German anthropologist	1842-1916
1843	Otto Hirschfeld	1863	1863	1917	German epigraphist and professor of ancient history	1843-1922
1843	Фёдор Корш	1864	1864	1915	Russian classical philologist, Slavist, orientalist, poetry expert, poet-translator	1843-1915
1843	Esaias Tegnér Jr.	1865	1865	1919	Swedish linguist and theologian	1843-1928
1843	Johannes Schmidt	1865	1865	1901	German linguist	1843-1901
1843	Julien Vinson	1866		1926	French linguist (languages of India, mainly Tamil, and also in the Basque language)	1843-1926
1843	Louis Léger	1866		1923	French writer and pioneer in Slavic studies	1843-1923
1843	Julius Lessing	1866		1908	German art historian and the first director of the Berliner Kunstgewerbemuseum (Museum of Decorative Arts in Berlin)	1843-1908
1843	Florimond Van Duyse	1867	1867	1910	Belgian lawyer, composer and musicologist	1843-1910
1843	Ernest Chantre	1867		1910	French prominent archaeologist and anthropologist.	1843-1924
1843	Eugen Prym	1868	1868	1913	German orientalist, who specialized in Semitic languages, especially Arabic and Aramaic	1843-1913
1843	Ernst Wülcker	1868	1868	1894	German archivist and lexicographer	1843-1895
1843	Wilhelm Wisser	1869	1869	1908	German teacher and dialectologist, collector of Low German legends and fairy tales	1843-1935
1843	Theodor Gartner	1870		1913	Austrian linguist, Romance philologist and professor (Ukrainian language)	1843-1925
1843	Richard Otto Zöpffel	1871		1891	Estonian Baltic German church historian and theologian	1843-1891
1843	Eugène Revillout	1874		1913	French Egyptologist	1843-1913
1843	Louis Duchesne	1876		1910	French priest , philologist, teacher and a critical historian of Christianity and Roman Catholic liturgy and institutions	1843-1922
1843	Thomas William Rhys Davids	1880		1922	British English scholar of the Pāli language and founder of the Pāli Text Society	1843-1922
1843	Evald Tang Kristensen	1880	No	1924	Danish folklore collector and author	1843-1929
1843	Georgios Hatzidakis	1882	1882	1923	Greek philologist, father of linguistics in Greece	1843-1941
1843	Vincent Arthur Smith	1887	1919	1920	Irish Indologist and art historian	1843-1920

1843	Dmitry Anuchin	1889	1889	1915	Russian anthropologist, ethnographer, archaeologist, and geographer	1843-1923
1844	Ernst Windisch	1867	1867	1918	German classical philologist and comparative linguist who specialised in Sanskrit, Celtic and Indo-European studies	1844-1918
1844	Rufino José Cuervo	1867		1910	Colombian writer, linguist, and philologist	1844-1911
1844	Bernhard Gerth	1868	1868	1911	German educator and classical philologist	1844-1911
1844	Carl Hermann Ethé	1868		1914	German orientalist best known for his catalogues of Islamic manuscripts and his studies and German translations of Persian poetry	1844-1917
1844	Ignazio Guidi	1870		1919	Italian orientalist	1844-1935
1844	Julius Wellhausen	1870	1870	1918	German biblical scholar and orientalist	1844-1918
1844	Steinar Schjøtt	1870	1870	1915	Norwegian educator, philologist and lexicographer	1844-1920
1844	Gustav Gröber	1871	1871	1911	German Romance philologist	1844-1911
1844	Alexander von Zagareli	1872	1872	1929	Georgian linguist	1844-1929
1844	Wendelin Foerster	1872	1872	1915	Austrian philologist and Romance scholar	1844-1915
1844	Andrew Harper	1872		1924	British Scottish–Australian biblical scholar, teacher, and school principal	1844-1936
1844	Émile Picot	1873		1918	French Romance philologist	1844-1918
1844	Hugo Andresen	1874	1874	1912	German Romance philologist and medievalist	1844-1918
1844	Milton W. Humphreys	1874	1874	1912	American early scholar of Ancient Greek and Latin in the United States	1844-1928
1844	Henry Eyster Jacobs	1878		1920	American religious educator, Biblical commentator and Lutheran theologian	1844-1932
1844	Gabriel Monod	1888	1888	1912	French medievalist	1844-1912